

Understanding and Evolving Scientific Applications and Workflows

Assessment
Playbook

SURF

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Introduction

Workflows provide a unifying abstraction through which scientific applications can be described, designed, employed, and continuously evolved. This abstraction enables researchers to focus on their scientific challenges and entrust technical details and infrastructure composition to the service providers.

A workflow-centric approach accelerates time-to-insight and informs the co-design of future infrastructures, ensuring that computational platforms evolve in step with the needs of science.

By placing workflows at the center, we are better able to support both the current needs and future challenges of scientific research.

This playbook serves as a practical tool to map how research processes and workflows unfold, how they interact with organizational and infrastructural requirements, and how they can be supported by solutions and services. In doing so, it helps researchers articulate their needs clearly, and guides infrastructure providers in aligning resources, technologies, and strategies with the ever-evolving scientific landscape.

Goal of the Playbook

The purpose of this playbook is to provide a structured framework for engaging with domain scientists, developers, and other stakeholders around the question about how we can support their current and future scientific ambitions with new services and infrastructure. By framing discussions through a layered approach, the playbook helps to:

- Capture the scientific intent and context behind research activities.
- Translate research challenges and needs into operational and computational workflows.
- Separate the requirements of solutions from specific technological implementations.
- Map those solutions onto concrete services and tools.
- Identify gaps and opportunities for new services and infrastructure co-design.

The first goal of using this playbook is to conduct an initial intake that captures a complete overview across all relevant topics, from scientific context to required services and tools.

A second goal is to kickstart a collaborative design and engineering process that develops the next generation of scientific applications and workflows.

By engaging domain scientists, support staff, and infrastructure providers in a co-creative process, we envision how workflows, tools, and services should evolve over the short, medium to long term. This forward-looking perspective ensures that we actively co-design the pathway toward future scientific and technological requirements, anticipating new challenges, modes of collaboration and technical solutions.

Furthermore, the playbook and its intended outcomes are designed to be iterative over time. Revisiting the discussion after 3, 5, 10 years allows research communities and infrastructure providers to evaluate progress, identify what has evolved, and redesign workflows, solutions, or services accordingly. This long-term perspective ensures that the playbook remains a living tool that evolves together with scientific and technological developments.

Last but not least, this playbook is not about prescribing a single “right” process. Instead, its purpose is to facilitate conversations and data-capture that allows research communities to articulate their requirements, pain points, and aspirations in a systematic way, and helps infrastructure providers to address these needs and challenges through solutions and services.

The Framework behind this Playbook

The playbook uses a framework that is organized into four layers, reflecting the path from scientific intent to technical realization.

Each of these layers should be analyzed from a temporal perspective, i.e., capturing the current landscape, as well as the future design and engineering needs.

This means capturing how each layer operates today but also co-designing and engineering their evolution over time.

By using the layers to not only form a representation of the current landscape, but also a temporal and evolutionary perspective, we create a survey of the changes that need to be implemented to support future scientific challenges and ambitions.

In this way, the playbook becomes a tool for understanding the present and shaping the future of scientific applications and workflows.

How to use this Playbook

This playbook is designed as a flexible guide for engaging with researchers and stakeholders to capture the full picture of scientific applications and their workflows from the present to the future. It does not prescribe a single “right” path but instead provides a structured approach that can be adapted to different contexts.

The playbook steps follow the four layers of the framework introduced in the previous section. Each layer offers a perspective on the research process, from high-level goals to technical implementation.

Each step in the playbook consists of the following components:

Definition

What this layer entails, its purpose and what information to gather.

Key actions

An outline of actionable steps that help capture the essential information in each layer.

Key players

The type of roles that should be engaged at this step, i.e., the relevant internal and external stakeholders.

Output

The intended results and tangible outcomes produced in the analysis phase of each step of the playbook.

Facilitating questions

Prompts to guide discussions and ensure meaningful information is gathered. Note: these lists of questions are not exhaustive and can be extended.

Ways of using the Playbook

There are two approaches for going through the steps in this playbook:

1. Navigate the layers

Work across the layers in the preferred order, ideally starting from the research process and moving toward services. This is useful when capturing a full picture of a new scientific application and is the preferred approach when assessing a project or application for the first time.

2. Selective use

Focus only on specific layers, depending on the maturity of the application. For example, if the research process and workflows are already well understood, you can begin directly at the workflow definition or solutions layer. (Do ask yourself whether this understanding is based on verified knowledge, instead of assumptions.)

In addition, it is best to use the playbook collaboratively and iteratively:

Collaborative: Involve diverse stakeholders in each layer to ensure that both scientific intent and technical requirements are fully captured. The combination of multiple perspectives will improve the quality of the outcomes.

Iterative: Revisit layers as projects evolve. For example, new solutions may prompt updates in workflow definitions, or new research ambitions may redefine the process layer. When this happens, it is recommended to revisit this playbook to assess whether these changes affect the other layers of the framework.

Practical tips

Treat the playbook as a **conversation starter**, not just a checklist. Use the facilitating questions to stimulate discussion and uncover hidden assumptions or gaps.

Encourage **visual mappings** of workflows and solutions (e.g., diagrams, flowcharts) to complement written answers.

Capture not only the **current state** but also **aspirations and future directions**, since this can inform infrastructure planning and co-design.

Use the playbook as a **living document**: revisit and update it regularly as research challenges, technologies, and services evolve.

Playbook steps

Research Context & Process

Definition

The Research Context & Process captures the foundation of a scientific application: the scientific, organizational, and governance context that defines how research is conceived and carried out. It describes the scientific problem(s), project(s), or line of inquiry that researchers aim to explore in the present and future, as well as the institutional, policy, and collaborative structures that enable or constrain them.

A scientific application can be very specific (e.g., improving the efficiency of blade aerodynamics in wind farms) or broader (e.g., a research group's coordinated effort to address related questions through national or international collaborations and research infrastructures).

Key Actions

This step should define the scope, scientific intent, organizational context, constraints and ambitions. This step should also outline a high-level roadmap, identifying key milestones, planned phases, potential risks, and sustainability considerations. The goal is to capture how the research and its workflows are expected to evolve over time, ensuring cohesion between scientific goals, operational planning, and future infrastructure needs.

This step should define:

- The scope
- Scientific context
- Scientific and organizational/governance context
- Intent
- Constraints

Key Players

Example of roles that could be involved in this playbook step:

Scientists

Research Partnership Leads

Advisors

Funding and policy agencies

Relationship Managers

Research Support Staff

Output

The output of this step is a concise, structured summary that captures the scientific and organizational foundations of the research activity. It should synthesize the key points identified through the previous Key Actions and Facilitating Questions, translating them into a coherent description of the research context, purpose, and environment.

Example

The scope of this discussion is the *research group / project / collaboration* focused on *specific set of scientific problems*, funded by *agency/program*, and involving *key players*.

The work sits within the broader context of *scientific field / international initiative*, connecting to *related scientific fields, projects, or collaborations*.

The aim is to *present research ambitions* while navigating *current challenges and constraints*. The ambitions in the future are *medium-term ambitions* in 3-5 years and *long-term ambitions* in 10 years.

Facilitating Questions

Scope

- What should be the span in which you would like to define the Research Context & Process (e.g., at the level of an (inter)national consortium or research infrastructure, research group, project, or fine-grained experiment)?
- Are we focusing on your entire research group or program and its collective activities?
- Are we focusing on a formal funding program (e.g., NWO Large/Small Compute Application, Horizon Europe, LSRI, ERC Grant, etc.)?
- What methods, experiments, or approaches will you use to explore them? Will these evolve in the future?
- What are the main scientific resources or services you depend on (e.g., compute, storage, instruments)?
- What is the broader scientific or societal context of this research?
- How does this research connect to existing knowledge, disciplines, and ongoing initiatives?

Scientific Content

- What is the specific scientific application(s) you want to focus on (problem, project, or line of inquiry)?
- What are the main scientific questions or hypotheses you want to address (in the present, medium-term and long-term)?

Scientific and Organizational/Governance Context

- What funding opportunities or organizational structures (projects, collaborations) shape this work?
- Are there policy, governance, or legal frameworks that shape how the work is done?
- How might the scientific and organization/governance context change in the future?

Key Players

- Who are the key stakeholders (policy makers, funding bodies, research partners, technical experts, operational staff)?
- Who is part of the research team, and what roles or expertise are needed?

Challenges and Constraints

- What future scientific challenges do you anticipate beyond this project?
- What are the main challenges preventing progress today?
- What constraints (resources, infrastructure, skills, regulations) shape your work?
- What are the main risks or dependencies that could affect your project's progress or sustainability?

Research ambitions

- What are the research ambitions in the next 3, 5 and 10 years?
- What key milestones or phases do you foresee in achieving these ambitions?
- How do you plan to ensure the long-term sustainability of your research activities, data, or infrastructure?
- What would it look like if your research processes improve efficiency by 10/100/1000x?

Research Workflow & User Stories

Definition

The Research Workflow & User Stories layer transforms the research process into a set of functional and procedural workflows that describe how the research is carried out in practice. These workflows capture the sequence of scientific, organizational and administrative activities that together enable the research progress. At this stage, workflows are described independently of specific tools or computational implementations.

This step helps build a complete picture of the ecosystem that sustains research by encompassing both scientific and computational workflows as well as supporting and operationalizing workflows (e.g., processes that manage governance, collaboration and access). The aim is to create a clear, high-level model of how research activities are organized and executed, forming the foundation for translating them into technical workflows in the next step.

Key Actions

This step should identify and map an overview of the main workflows that make up the research process, highlighting how they interconnect and depend on one another. It should also identify the inputs, outputs, and decision points that define the flow of work, and capture representative user stories that illustrate the real-world experience of carrying out these workflows.

This step should define:

- Representative user stories illustrating each workflow
- The main scientific, operational, and governance workflows involved in the research process
- The relationships, dependencies, and possible parallelism between workflows
- Key inputs, outputs, and outcomes for each workflow
- Bottlenecks, pain points, or inefficiencies in current workflows
- Opportunities for improvement, automation, or optimization

Key Players

Example of roles that could be involved in this playbook step:

 Scientists

 Relationship Managers

 Research Support Staff

 Solution Architects

 Funding and policy agencies

 Advisors

 Data stewards

 Workflow engineers

 Research Partnership Leads

Output

A structured overview or visual representation of the research workflows that support the scientific process. It should illustrate how user stories translate into functional workflows, showing inputs, outputs, dependencies, and interactions between scientific, operational, and governance components.

This output typically includes:

A set of user stories, each describing how a specific actor interacts with the research process.

A workflow map connecting these user stories into higher-level research workflows (scientific, computational, and organizational).

Identification of inputs (data, instruments, resources), outputs (results, datasets, publications), and dependencies (approvals, policies, external collaborations).

Pain points and optimization opportunities identified through user experiences.

Facilitating Questions

User roles and experiences

- Who are the user roles involved in this workflow (e.g., domain scientists, data stewards, workflow engineers, policy officers)?
- Which user stories best describe how these roles engage with the research process from start to finish?
- What are their specific responsibilities and interactions within the workflow?
- How do you expect user roles, skills, and interactions to evolve in the next 3–10 years?
- What user roles, skills and interactions are required by the scientific ambitions in 3-10 years?

Research Process definition

- What are the main workflows that make up your research process (scientific, organizational, or policy-related)?
- What are the main inputs and outputs of each workflow (data, approvals, results, publications)?
- How do these workflows connect (sequence, dependencies, iteration)?
- How often are these workflows executed (once per project, repeated cycles, continuous)?
- What would it mean in practical terms to make this workflow 10×, 100×, or 1000× more productive?
- What emerging technologies or organizational changes could transform this workflow's productivity and user experience?

Challenges and bottlenecks

- What difficulties or inefficiencies do users encounter while carrying out their tasks (technical, organizational, or procedural)?
- Which stages of the workflow are most time-consuming, fragile, or error-prone?
- How do these issues affect overall research progress or collaboration?
- Which workflows are critical bottlenecks for progress?
- How do supporting workflows impact the research process and productivity?

Intermezzo

Up to this point, the playbook has focused on capturing the **scientific and organizational dimensions** of research workflows: how research is conceived, structured, and managed across people, institutions, and processes. These layers provide the essential context that explains **why** certain workflows exist and **how** they contribute to the scientific objectives of a project.

From the next step onward, the focus shifts toward the **computational and infrastructural realization** of these workflows. In this part of the playbook, we translate the functional and procedural descriptions gathered so far into **technical workflows**, those that define data movement, computational tasks, automation pipelines, and system dependencies.

While governance and organizational workflows remain relevant for the overall success of a Scientific Application, the following layers narrow in on the **technical implementation**: how research processes are expressed, executed, and supported through infrastructure, tools, and services.

Research Context & Process

Define the scientific context, goals, and constraints.

Research Workflow & User Stories

Describe high-level tasks that support the research process.

Workflow Definition & Solution Design

Translate tasks into concrete infrastructural and operational workflows and requirements.

Service & Tool Engineering

Map abstract solutions onto concrete services, technologies, and infrastructure.

Workflow Definition & Solution Design

Definition

The Workflow Definition & Solution Design translate research workflows into concrete computational and data workflows that can be executed on general compute and data infrastructures. At this level, the focus shifts from the scientific or organizational logic of the research process to its functional realization: defining tasks in terms of computational jobs, data movements, storage operations, and automation pipelines.

Workflow Definition & Solution Design captures the structure of tasks, their dependencies, and the resources they require (compute, data, storage, networking). It also considers how workflows are expressed and what level of automation or reproducibility is needed. The design should define the functional and non-functional requirements per component. Depending on the complexity of the workflow, peripheral systems, such as AAI and security, could also be included. By doing so, this step will result in a blueprint that allows research workflows to be mapped onto services and infrastructure.

Key Actions

In this step the Research workflows and user stories are broken down at the highest level of detail possible. The functional and non-functional requirements of a specific workflow and research ambition are determined. The architecture of the current state with the desired state in

the medium and long term are compared to make explicit which changes are required.

This step should define:

- A breakdown of research workflows and user stories into the smallest steps
- Relationships, dependencies, and possible parallelism of each step and between workflows
- Inputs, outputs, functional and non-functional requirements for each step
- Bottlenecks, pain points, or for the entire workflow and per step
- Opportunities for improvement, automation, or optimization

Key Players

Example of roles that could be involved in this playbook step:

- | | |
|---|---|
| Workflow Engineers |
| Admins from different teams |
| Solution Engineers |
| Research Software Engineers |
| Data Stewards | |

Output

The output of this step is a comprehensive technical representation of how workflows are realized as computational and data solutions. Include visual or architectural representations (e.g., diagrams, high-level design documents, and workflow specifications) that can be used for technical discussions and co-design with infrastructure teams. This output should:

- Provide a clear mapping of scientific and operational workflows into computational and data workflows, showing how each component contributes to the overall research process.
- Define the structure and dependencies between workflow elements, including task sequences, data flows, and interactions among compute, storage, network components, data spaces, etc.
- Identify the functional and non-functional requirements, such as automation, reproducibility, scalability, performance, and portability.
- Document gaps and bottlenecks between the current state and the desired future state, highlighting where new infrastructure, tools, or process redesigns are needed.

Facilitating Questions

Workflow structure

- Which parts of your current and ideal research workflows translate into computational or data workflows?
- What computational tasks are required (e.g., simulations, data preprocessing, training models, visualization)?
- What data workflows are needed (e.g., acquisition, transfer, cleaning, integration, archiving)?
- How do these computational and data workflows depend on each other?
- How does data move through the workflow? Which data management and storage functionalities are needed?
- How do the different compute, data and networking components in the workflow definition interact and integrate?
- What are the required inputs and expected outputs at each step?

Execution and automation

- What level of reproducibility is needed?
- Where are the opportunities for parallel execution?
- Which steps in the workflow definition can or should be semi/fully automated, and which can remain manual?
- Which workflow description approaches or tools (e.g., scripts, workflow languages, pipelines) are used today?
- Can the workflow execution benefit from orchestration?

Requirements and constraints

- What are the critical bottlenecks (compute, data movement, storage, networking)?
- What are the compute, data and networking requirements for this workflow?
- Are there domain-specific requirements in this workflow definition (e.g., specific data formats or data sources)?

- What peripheral functionalities does this workflow require (AAI, security, monitoring, logging, etc.)?
- Are there non-technical factors (e.g., political, cultural or governance-related) that influence the requirements and constraints of the workflow?
- How portable should the workflow be across different infrastructures?

Evolution

- What is the current solution for this workflow (if any) and how should it evolve in the medium and long term?
- How could changes in the scientific ambition affect the current workflow definition and solution design in the medium and long term?
- What trends in the scientific domain could have an impact on the current solution?

Service and Tool Engineering

Definition

Service components and tools refer to the concrete infrastructure components that together implement the requirements of a workflow definition and solution design. These infrastructure components span both software and hardware implementations. The purpose of this step is to determine which services are best suited for fulfilling the requirements of the Workflow Definition and Solution Design. These might be existing services or ones that still need to be developed or purchased. Whereas in the Workflow Definition & Solution Design layer the components are functionally described (e.g., “a GPU accelerator that supports partitioning” or “a virtualization platform”), in this layer a specific piece of software and/or hardware is selected (e.g., “NVIDIA GH200” or “Openstack”).

Key Actions

This step should define the concrete implementation of the workflow definition and solution design. After comparing the current state of service components and tools with the desired state, a plan needs to be formulated for bridging the gap at an infrastructure and service level. This could mean identifying which services and tooling meet the requirements of the workflow definition and solution design, comparing the different options and deciding between options based on technical and nontechnical criteria.

Alternatively, it could be a matter of specifying a new type of application that should be developed or a new way of composing existing infrastructure and services.

This step should define:

- A breakdown of the current and desired services, tools and infrastructure per workflow step
- Relationships and dependencies between tools, services and infrastructure
- Bottlenecks, pain points, or for current tools, services and infrastructure
- Opportunities for improvement of tools, services and infrastructure

Key Players

Example of roles that could be involved in this playbook step:

- | | |
|---|--|
| Solution Engineers |
| Developers |
| Procurement |
| Research Software Engineers | |

Output

The output of this step is a detailed technical and strategic articulation of how the workflow's requirements are implemented through concrete services, tools, and infrastructure components. It captures the bridge between solution design and operational realization, ensuring that each workflow element is supported by the most suitable technological and organizational means. This output should:

- Deliver a comprehensive mapping between workflow requirements and existing or planned services and tools, clarifying how each component supports functional and performance needs.
- Provide a gap analysis identifying where current services fall short of supporting the defined workflows and what new services, integrations, or upgrades are required.
- Outline strategic options for implementation, e.g., reuse of existing solutions, procurement of commercial products, or development of new tools or services.
- Practical blueprints for implementation and planning, supporting both immediate operational decisions and long-term co-design between research communities and infrastructure providers.
- Define future paths that show how selected services and tools should evolve over time to meet medium- and long-term scientific ambitions.

Facilitating Questions

Gap analysis

- How do the requirements of this workflow and solution map to the current services?
- To what extent can the current service portfolio support the requirements of this solution?
- Are there gaps in the service portfolio that either prevent the support of a specific solution or would improve the support of this solution?
- Which services are no longer able to support current and future solutions?
- Do we need better interoperability, integration and standardization of services to support this particular solution?

Requirements definition

- What are the end-user demands of the service we are looking for (user experience, documentation, ease of use, etc.)?
- What are the operational demands of the service we are looking for (maintainability, cost, integration with tools, etc)?
- What is required from the service or tooling based on the future scientific ambitions defined in the previous layers?
- What is required from the service in terms of scalability, availability, security and observability?

Service selection

- Are there several new or existing services that meet the requirements of the solution? How should we evaluate and compare them?
- Are there several solutions and/or workflows that could benefit from a new service?
- Can we reuse or buy the required service, or does it need to be developed?

- Are there non-technical factors (e.g., political, cultural or governance-related) that should be taken into account when selecting a service or tool?

Strategic planning

- Are there technical trends and developments in the area of this service that should inform the layers above?
- How will (or should) the service and tooling change in the medium and long term?
- How does this service align with our strategy and technology roadmap?

Next steps

After finishing the assessment in this playbook, it should be clear what the current and future ambitions of a scientific application are, and what is required at the solution and service level to support these ambitions. However, this initial assessment is only a first step, and more work needs to be done in follow-up processes. The following processes—ordered from high uncertainty and complexity to low—can take the input from this playbook and work towards solutions that support the workflows needed by the research process:

Co-design

A process in which researchers, infrastructure and technology providers collaborate to find a solution that can support new workflows.

└ *When to apply?* If the changes required by the scientific ambitions have a high level of uncertainty, and benefit from an agile process that can adapt to new learnings.

Solution architecture and engineering

A method for mapping the requirements of a workflow onto a portfolio of services and tools, and the implementation of this mapping.

└ *When to apply?* When the required services and tools are already in place, but they need to be composed, configured and/or integrated to suit a particular workflow.

Product development

The creation of new services and tools or the addition of new features to existing services and tools.

└ *When to apply?* If the required changes are limited to a single component that either does not exist or needs additional functionality to support the workflow.

Service delivery

The process of making services available to users.

└ *When to apply?* When the services and tools required by the workflow are already available and only need to be made accessible to users through existing channels.

Another approach for continuing the work started in the playbook would be to evolve the different layers of the framework separately. For instance, each layer could be assigned to a different team to work out in more detail and develop more mature action plans.

Finally, keep in mind that this playbook can be used iteratively and that it could be worthwhile to reassess a research project in the future. As always, playbooks and frameworks are tools that can and should be applied flexibly as the situation requires.

The background features a white page with several decorative elements: a purple horizontal line at the top, a yellow horizontal line below it, and a yellow L-shaped line forming a frame on the right and bottom. On the left, there are yellow, blue, and purple rounded rectangular shapes. On the right, there are large blue and green rounded shapes. At the bottom, there are yellow, green, and blue horizontal lines and shapes.

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